

Simultaneous determination of antimalarial artemisinin, dihydroartemisinin and arteether using reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography

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A simple and rapid reversed phase HPLC method using photodiode array detection has been developed for simultaneous quantitation of α -arteether (3a), β -arteether (3b), its chemical precursor artemisinin (2) and intermediate precursors α -dihydroartemisinin (DHA) (1a) and β -dihydroartemisinin (1b). The method is capable of separating two isomeric forms of DHA (α, β), arteether (α, β) and artemisinin in a single run. The method is suitable for monitoring the reaction product in the preparation of arteether using artemisinin via dihydroartemisinin.

Search for the development of new antimalarial resulted in the isolation of a novel sesquiterpene lactone with an endoperoxide function artemisinin from the traditional chinese medicinal herb qinghao, *Artemisia annua* L. (Asteraceae). Presently, artemisinin and its derivatives are receiving considerable attention because of their activity against resistant strains of *Plasmodium falciparum* and efficacy against cerebral malaria¹. Artemether and arteether, semisynthetic derivatives of artemisinin, play critical role in the treatment of *P. falciparum* malaria in areas where multi-drug resistance has been developed².

Dihydroartemisinin is a semisynthetic product of artemisinin which has further been derivatized to form more potent antimalarial derivative arteether, which has advantage of being more liposoluble than artemisinin. Arteether (a mixture of β - and α -isomers of arteethers) has recently been released³ as a potent antimalarial drug in the treatment of cerebral malaria in India. HPLC methods available for simultaneous quantitation of artemisinin and its methyl/ethyl ethers are mainly based on electrochemical detection^{2,4}. The drawback of the technique is the requirement of rigorous deoxygenation of the system and sample injection and also, the technique is costly and faces problem of base line stabilization. In our efforts towards developing liquid chromatographic procedures⁵ for plant drug analysis, we report here a reversed phase liquid chromatographic method for the simultaneous determination of arteether (α - and β -isomers), artemisinin and dihydroartemisinin (α - and β -isomers). The method is suitable in monitoring the reaction product conversion of artemisinin to arteether via intermediate dihydroartemisinin.

1a : R = - α OH **1b** : R = - β OH
3a : R = - α OCH₂CH₃, **3b** : R = - β OCH₂CH₃

Results and Discussion

A number of HPLC chromatographic conditions were studied to optimize the simultaneous separation of artemisinin, DHA and arteether. A Shimadzu C₁₈ reversed phase was shown to give a base line separation within a 20 min run time by using acetonitrile-H₂O-1,4-dioxane (65 : 32 : 3, v/v/v) as mobile phase. Fig. 1 illustrates the separation of compounds 1-3 in an artificial mixture of standards and a reaction product. Peaks of compounds in reaction product, checked via addition of standards, were symmetrical. Artemisinin, α - and β -DHA and α - and β -arteether were eluted at 6.04, 4.39, 5.59, 11.39 and 17.47 min, respectively. Average recoveries for artemisinin, α -DHA,

Fig 1. RPLC separation of compounds 1a, 1b, 2, 3a, 3b in an artificial mixture of pure compounds (A) and 2 mg/ml and a reaction product (B)

β -DHA, α -arteether and β -arteether were 97.0, 96.8, 97.2, 96.4 and 98.0%, respectively. For the examination of recoveries, known amounts of freshly prepared solutions of pure compounds 1-3 were added to the reaction product and the quantitation repeated four times. The peak purity of compounds 1-3 were tested using a photodiode array detector: 1a, purity up 0.9992, down 0.9999; 1b, up 0.9997, down 1.0000; 2, up 1.0000, down 1.0000; 3a, up 0.9999, down 0.9996; 3b, up 0.9999, down 0.9999. Peak purity results of 1-3 were found satisfactory.

Calibration curves of peak areas versus concentrations were linear for compounds 1-3 (Table 1) with correlation coefficients (r) values between 0.998 and 0.999. Linearity was determined by using five concentrations in a working range of 2–20 μ g each of compounds 1-3. Detection limit, determined by estimating the minimal mass of each compound that can be quantified, were 0.15–0.25 μ g/injection for 1-3.

The proposed method has been applied in monitoring the product purity in a number of reactions in the synthesis of α - and β -arteether from artemisinin via dihydroartemisinin.

Table 1 Column performance and linear regression data for compounds 1-3*

Compd no	R_t	Recovery (%) \pm S D	Capacity factor	No of theor plate counts	Linear regression equation ^a	r
1a	4.39	96.8 \pm 1.2	1.03	4669	$Y = 11682.0X + 1702.4$	0.999
1b	5.59	97.2 \pm 0.8	1.56	5311	$Y = 4911.9X + 214.0$	0.998
2	6.04	97.0 \pm 2.0	1.77	5257	$Y = 23712.0X + 5223.4$	0.998
3a	11.39	96.4 \pm 1.8	4.17	6541	$Y = 6487.1X + 3915.2$	0.998
3b	17.47	98.0 \pm 1.0	6.93	6750	$Y = 8724.0X + 5481.8$	0.998

* R_t = Retention time, r = regression

^aNumber of data points, 5, number of replicates, 3

The present analytical method for the determination of artemisinin, dihydroartemisinin and arteether is suitable for monitoring the purity of a reaction product in the synthesis of antimalarial drug arteether using artemisinin via dihydroartemisinin.

Experimental

Standard artemisinin was isolated from the plant *Artemisia annua*, grown⁶ in C.I.M.A.P., Lucknow. Dihydroartemisinin was synthesized by reduction of artemisinin with sodium borohydride⁷. Arteether was synthesized by etherification of dihydroartemisinin⁸. All solvents used were of HPLC grade (J. T. Baker).

A. annua leaves were extracted in hexane and the dried hexane extract was column chromatographed over silica gel using hexane-ethyl acetate (90 : 10) as eluent to isolate pure artemisinin.

Artemisinin (10 g) in methanol (40 ml) was cooled in an ice-bath (0–5 $^{\circ}$). To the cooled solution sodium borohydride (0.25 g) was added in small portions over a period of 30 min and the solution stirred at 0–5 $^{\circ}$ for 3 h. The reaction mixture was neutralized with 30% acetic acid/methanol and evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The white residue was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 \times 50 ml). The combined ethyl acetate extracts were filtered and evaporated to dryness to give white needles of dihydroartemisinin, m.p. 153 $^{\circ}$.

A solution of dihydroartemisinin (5 g, 0.016 mmol) in dry ethanol (25 ml) was treated with chlorotrimethylsilane (0.5 ml, 0.004 mmol) and kept at room temperature for 4 h. The reaction mixture was diluted with dichloromethane (200 ml) and washed with saturated sodium acetate solution (50 ml) followed by water (2 \times 50 ml). The organic phase was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the solvent evaporated. The residue was dissolved in hexane-ethyl acetate (96 : 4) and filtered through a silica gel (50 g) column to yield α/β -arteether as a viscous oil.

A Shimadzu LC-8A gradient HPLC instrument (Dual

Note

LC-8A pump model), controlled by a CBM-10A interface module, Rheodyne manual injector 7725 I, a 20 µl sample loop and a SPD M-10 AVP (Shimadzu) photodiode array detector was used. Data were collected and analyzed using a Class LC-10 Work Station equipped with a Pentium computer. A Millipore system was used for the filtration of solvents. Analysis was performed on a Shimadzu C₁₈ column (250 mm × 4.0 mm i.d., 5 µm). The composition of mobile phase was optimized by varying the percentage of acetonitrile in water, resulting in the following operating conditions : acetonitrile-H₂O-1,4-dioxane (65 : 32 : 3, v/v/v); flow rate, 1.2 ml/min; column temperature, 26°; detector wavelength, 235 nm, the absorption maxima close to all the compounds.

Stock solutions of standard artemisinin, DHA and ar-teether were prepared as 2 µg/µl concentration in methanol for the preparation of standard curve and quantitation. A 5 µg/µl solution of reaction product in methanol was prepared for analysis.

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